

Mausoleum of Hasan Baba Tekke in Tempí

also known as “Hasan Baba Türbesi”

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Islamic Traditions, Sufism, Bektashi, Religious Place, Abrahamic, Greece, Thessaly, Islam, Language, Turkic, Common Turkic, Oghuz, Nuclear Oghuz, West Oghuz, Turkish, Ottoman Turkish

The mausoleum of the Bektashi dervish Hasan Baba located in Tempí was a part of a broader site, Hasan Baba Tekke, a shrine dedicated to him. It might be a cenotaph of the founding father of the shrine, Hasan Baba. The architectural remains are dated back to the first half of the 15th century. The shrine of Hasan Baba has been quite important for the region of Thessaly and the nearby village of Tempí was named "Baba" after it, until 1927. The mausoleum was recently restored but not open to the public without prior permission.

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2026 CE

Region: Tempí, Thessaly

Region tags: Balkans, Greece, Thessaly

The tomb of Hasan Baba is located on the Vale of Tempí in Thessaly. The location is close to the village of Ambelakia, which flourished in the 18th and 19th centuries. The region is also close to Mount Olympus and the Pineios River.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

The society in which the religious place is located is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Bektashi Dervishes and local muslims

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Allah

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– I don't know

Notes: Possibly

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– Yes

Notes: The Bektashi Dervishes

Were the structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

– Other [specify]: Bektashi Dervishes

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– I don't know

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– I don't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: The Ottoman conquest of Thessaly

Reference: Eyice, Semavi. "Hasan Baba Tekkesi". TDV İslam Ansiklopedisi, no. 16 (1997): 290–91.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Water source

Notes: It is situated next to the Pineios River.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: The village of Tempí, or "Baba" prior to 1927.

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Plantings

– Clearing

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Choulia, Souzana. "Hasan Baba Tekke." In *Ottoman Architecture in Greece*, 203. Athens: Hellenic Ministry of Culture, 2008.

– Source 2: Eyice, Semavi. "Hasan Baba Tekkesi." *TDV İslam Ansiklopedisi*, no. 16 (1997): 290–91.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– I don't know

Notes: Restorations not excavations.

Has this place been looted:

– Yes

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 3 Description: The name change of the village of Tempi from "Baba" to "Tempi" and the date of the change.
- Source 1 Description: The reopening of the archeological site, as a reportage of the Hellenic Broadcasting Corporation (ERT)
- Source 2 URL: <https://archive.apan.gr/gr/data/Accompanying-Item/28437>
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.ertnews.gr/perifereiakoi-stathmoi/larisa/anoikse-gia-to-koino-o-tekes-tou-xasan-mpampa-sta-tempi/>
- Source 2 Description: The Hasan Baba Tekke on the website of "The Panorama Cultural Society" [APAN Archive]
- Source 3 URL: <https://settlement-renames.eie.gr/renames/>

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Clearing

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: Hasan Baba Tekke

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

Notes: The mosque and the other buildings of the tekke, after 1819 and for unknown

reasons.

Reference: Choulia, Souzana. "Hasan Baba Tekke". In *Ottoman Architecture in Greece*, 203. Athens: Hellenic Ministry of Culture, 2008.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– Once

↳ In modernity

– Other (date-range):: 2007-2026

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Bricks and mortar

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 9

Reference: Choulia, Souzana. "Hasan Baba Tekke". In *Ottoman Architecture in Greece*, 203. Athens: Hellenic Ministry of Culture, 2008.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– I don't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Lime

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Glass

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

Reference: Eyice, Semavi. "Hasan Baba Tekkesi". TDV Islam Ansiklopedisi, no. 16 (1997): 290–91.

Reference: Choulia, Souzana. "Hasan Baba Tekke". In *Ottoman Architecture in Greece*, 203. Athens: Hellenic Ministry of Culture, 2008.

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions a formal dedication:

– I don't know

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Limited information on the inscriptions.

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– I don't know

↳ Other type of decoration:

–Yes [specify]: Architectural decorations

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs
– I don't know

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy
– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]
– Other [specify]: Limited information on the internal decorations.

↳ Are there statues present:
– No

↳ Are there paintings present:
– I don't know

↳ Are there mosaics present:
– I don't know

↳ Is the decoration figural:
A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted
– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:
A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.
– No

- ↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries
 - No

Iconography

- Are there distinct features of the iconography:
 - No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

- Is this place a tomb/burial:
 - Yes

- Are grave goods present:
 - No

- Are formal burials present:
 - Yes

- ↳ Domestic context:
 - Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity
 - Yes

- ↳ As cenotaphs:
 - I don't know
 - Notes: Probably. There is limited access and information on this monument.

- ↳ In cemetery:
 - No

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Veneration of a Bektashi dervish.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– I don't know

Notes: Veneration of the dead, not worship.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Supernatural Beings

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is a supreme high god present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– I don't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– I don't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– I don't know

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– No

Notes: Historically, yes, but not anymore.

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Notes: By the Hellenic Ministry of Culture.

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Religious Specialists

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the place was used to train dervishes, but not anymore.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: Ruins of a dervish lodge.

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The Hellenic Ministry of Culture.

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Bureaucracy

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

Notes: The Hellenic Ministry of Culture.

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Mausoleum of Hasan Baba Tekke in Tempi, Eyice, Semavi. "Hasan Baba Tekkesi". TDV Islam Ansiklopedisi, no. 16 (1997): 290-91.

Reference: Mausoleum of Hasan Baba Tekke in Tempi, Choulia, Souzana. "Hasan Baba Tekke". In *Ottoman Architecture in Greece*, 203. Athens: Hellenic Ministry of Culture, 2008.

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Other [specify]: The Ottoman conquest of Thessaly, Eyice, Semavi. "Hasan Baba Tekkesi". TDV Islam Ansiklopedisi, no. 16 (1997): 290-91. ,

Reference: Yes, Choulia, Souzana. "Hasan Baba Tekke". In *Ottoman Architecture in Greece*, 203. Athens: Hellenic Ministry of Culture, 2008. , ,